

Urban sprawl on agricultural land in Iraq – The factors and impacts
A study of Karkh area in the city of Baghdad

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ABSTRACT:

This research is the scientific in-depth study of factors and effects of urban sprawl on agricultural areas in Iraq, in addition to studying the reasons for that crawl within the political and economic changes in Iraq between 2003 and 2015, taking into consideration the specificity of the social situation of the inhabitants of the region. This subject acquires its importance from the importance of understanding the future developments of the city and the countryside in order to develop mechanisms to address the causes and legal loopholes that lead to this phenomenon thus the development of mechanisms to help tackle these problems. The research provides an preliminary understanding of the extent and the effects of the phenomenon and its effects on the surrounding environment in both the short and the long terms thus enabling to address these problems and to reduce the effects throughout laws, regulations and policies adopted by the state.

The research methodology adopted by this research is based on statistical and geographic analysis using statistical and geographical information gathered by field study or acquired from third parties and governmental organizations as a source of data, The research uses the Geographical Information System (GIS) in order to achieve an in-depth study on the research problem through a series of objectives:

1. A brief definition about urban sprawl, its history, and the potential impact and effects in relation to the political and economic changes as well as the social on cultural characteristics of Iraq in particular.
2. Reviewing academic literature about urban sprawl in the world and Iraq in particular, and the main reasons leading to the increasing of this phenomenon.
3. Reviewing legal loopholes that have been used to encroach upon agricultural land. Through which the review laws which have been overlooked for humanitarian reasons.
4. Choosing a casestudy site (palm groves in the Karkh district of Baghdad) / neighboring areas "Topchi, housing, entrance Kazimiyah" as an example of urban sprawl between the year 2003 and the year 2015 and the changes that have occurred in the region through the GIS system analysis. And then study these changes to understand its effects on the countryside and the city.

Finally the research ends with a set of conclusions, final key points and proposals for future research on the subject of the study.

INTRODUCTION:

The first object of this research deals with the phenomenon of urban sprawl particularly the residential squatter on agricultural land within the concept of squatters housing and their synonyms with a set of definitions.

The second object includes academic literature discussion on the causes that lead to the evolution and increasing of residential sprawl phenomenon within its general and private causes related to the demographic, planning, economic and political reasons.

The third object presents a massive view on encroaching of these settlements within physical, social and legal characters including the causes and the ways of evolution through local characteristic models properties analysis in Baghdad by taking the example of palm orchards areas within the Karkh district of Baghdad and the neighboring area sites (Topchi – Al-Eskan) in particular.

The fourth object includes discussion and analysis of the subject of study (AL Alshalchia at the East of Al-Eskan district) to identify the proportion and extend of the phenomenon of residential sprawl in addition to the main economic, social , legal and administrative loopholes that contributed to the emergence and extent of such phenomenon .

Finally the research summaries themain points within this search mentioning the most important and potential influences for this phenomenon.

PART 1: THE IDEA OF URBAN SPRAWL

The word “Sprawl “ in the Dictionary refers to the state of transmission of an object from one place to another within the concept of moving or expanding. In architecture it keeps the same concept in addition to the idea of functional changing of using land . It also refers to the impact of land use changing as being green agricultural spaces not intended for future expansion.

Synonyms of (informal) residential sprawl Idiomatically : -

Some differences may be observed in residential sprawl informal labeling such as (slums, Squatter settlements , low- income housing This labeling differences is based upon the circumstances , the reasons and characteristics of their emergence as well as the government policies and its legislations towards such Squatter settlements.

UN HABITAT, 1995 Program defines Squatter settlements as "residential areas that contained illegally build houses on encroached land seized by squatters, theses settlements are usually unplanned and lack of basic services, these settlements can be found at the outskirts and neglected land .The outskirts of cities owned by state or private property "Bogu, Enkela, (2003).

This definition as we noticed focused on the legal status of this type of housing and whereabouts in addition to its urban characteristics.

These settlements defined by (Chome, 2002) as "urban settlements for those with low-income, created through seizing a land or property with the absence of legal and legitimate approvals that enable them to invest , build , and provide the land with infrastructure services.

Chome definition focused on social , economic status of the settlements dwellers in addition to the legal and Constructional characteristics status .

A thesis submitted by Mayada A.B (2008) presented many synonyms for the definition of squatters housing terms such as :

(Informal Settlement), (Illegal Subdivision), (Settlement Un controlling), (Slums), (Spontaneous Settlement) and others.

The term (Informal Settlement) defines as "residential areas where a group of housing units built on seized land illegally and illegitimately " (Mayada A.B Thesis (2008).

Illegal Subdivision defines as " illegally and illegitimately seized land . These lands usually located on the outskirts state land and they are unoccupied vast lands and difficult to invest for being expensive in most cases" " (Mayada A.B Thesis (2008).The Draft Report of Economic and Social Commission of the United Nations (FAO) dated (September 25, 2003) in Bangkok, defines the term “ squatter settlement” as "a residential area located in an urban location,

inhabited illegitimately by the poor people that have no proprietorship. These squatter settlements suffering from the lack of social and basic infrastructure services."

Squatters settlements define as "group of constructed houses on encroached land. This type of housing tends to exist in the outskirts of the major cities. These Squatters settlements' characterized by different social, structural and material characteristics. They are usually built by available materials like wooden or tin boxes and the rubble of other building materials, lacking basic technical and social infrastructure services."

At the first and second definition we noticed a confirmation on the legal and legitimate status of the constructed land, as well as the location of these settlements.

The third definition refers to the economic status of the squatters as well as the legal status of the settlement.

The fourth definition refers to the specification of squatters settlements' location as well as the social and physical isolation case of these settlements, in addition to the specification of the building materials nature which are unsustainable in many cases

The term (Slums) defined by UN HABITAT Organization report (UN Habitat –The State Of Arab City 2003) as "General context to describe a wide range of low-income settlements or the living conditions of poor people."

It is noticed that this term (Slums) differs from the term (Settlement squatter) as the first one is related to the social and economic status of the dwellers, while the second one is related to the legal aspects as well as other properties related to both constructional situation of the settlement and the social and economical status of the dwellers. The Classification of synonymous terms to squatters' settlements' depending on the specific criteria (" (Mayada A.B Thesis (2008))

From the above definitions we conclude that the residential sprawl has two types (official) which is planned both urbanely and administratively and (officious) which has no planning or committed by society without any legal approvals. These concerns are to be covered by its causes and effects within this research.

Terminology Classification	Standards
Informal Settlement	Legal standard
Illegitimacy Settlement	Legal Standard
unplanned Settlement uncontrolled Settlement	planning and organizing standard
Spontaneous Settlement	Physics Standard
Slums	Social standard
Low-Income Settlement	

PART 2: THE REASONS BEHIND THE EMERGENCE OF THE RESIDENTIAL SPRAWL

PHENOMENON

There are many reasons associated with the emergence and expanding of the residential sprawl phenomenon which are related to the social, political or environmental factors concerning the nature of the society of the country.

Kahachi (2012) summarizes these factors in Third World Countries in general and in Arab Homeland and Iraq in specific as following:

1. Natural reasons as population increasing, rapid urbanization and migration from countryside to the city related to employment opportunities, services and mechanization of agriculture and so many others.

2. Political reasons such as wars and giving priority to one's interests and the partisan interests upon the country's interest which conclude to the weakness or un effectiveness of the housing plans handling the situation of housing crisis. In addition to these reasons is the lack of security that leads the emergence of residential areas in which dwellers relates to each other by family relationships.

3- Economic reasons as low level income, increasing poverty and the "budget deficit" rising upon the deterioration of the private sector as a result of many factors like wars and unfair laws.

4- Demographic and social reasons as tribalism nature of some dwellers that requires housing within communities and larger population of the same tribe as well as socially correlated individuals with each other in a way that prevent or reduce housing opportunities in other cities or remote areas.

5- Absence or weakness of the planning and implementation of housing legislations and policies which are supposed to contribute to resolve housing issues, specifically the poorer classes while it is exploited by some beneficiaries in order to achieve financial gains.

These policies and legislations related to the legislators point of view of the encroachment and the philosophy of dealing with Squatters:

A. It is either came from dealing with squatters in a way that ensure humanitarian side through supporting the right to own homeless squatters then provide them with land patent or supporting them by compensation.

B. Or came from considering the case (Squatters) of bad effectiveness to the city and the rest of the dwellers and therefore the government obliged to use coercive treatments as depriving the squatters from their homes in these areas without any financial compensation or providing them with alternatives Jain, Sadhana (2005).

United Nations UN-Habitat (2012) report indicates that these reasons are among many other reasons that have a significant role in the emergence of the residential sprawl phenomenon not only in Iraq but also at the level of the Third World Countries including Arab world

The United Nations report with the help of the World Bank (2004) in Washington in its twelfth session has submitted a program in which programs and policies aimed at handling with the problem are discussed. The discussion include examples of several countries communities as follows:-

- Mortgages Program in Philippine and the Community-based Initiatives for Housing and Local Development (COBILD) where these programs provide credit certificates for lands for residential purposes.

• At the same time, some governments developed plans for the resettlement of squatters under rehabilitation programs. Sri Lanka Government has legislated a number of legislations to enable the inhabitants of these settlements to have their Settlement deed taking into consideration the rehabilitation and equipping these settlements with appropriate services.

On the other hand some of the negative experiences had been submitted in the government policies, including:

• Bangladesh government take a compulsory demolition policies to squatter settlements', in addition to the expulsion procedures without providing any alternatives as well as imposing high fines relatively.

• Violence use against squatters in Egypt through the use of security forces to evacuate the entire settlements.

There are some other political aspects that somehow affect the emergence and extend of squatter settlements' like exploiting the dwellers of these settlements need by the provision of services offers or property deeds or even to issue an act of indemnity for social or political purposes as supporting in elections campaigns and then for one advantages. This phenomenon shows clearly in squatter settlements' at most Developing Countries Carazzai, Valeria (2002).

THE CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESIDENTIAL SPRAWL AREAS IN ACADEMIC LITERATURE

a- urban characteristics:

- The houses are small in size.
- The nature of the land, as many settlements suffers from the dangers of floods and other natural disasters (Sharif, 2004).
- These areas are described as distorted housing areas, as the dwellers used any materials available for building as (clay, wood, tin, cardboard, or other urban waste. Srinivas, (1991).
- These settlements completely lacking the essential elements of residential areas as paved roads and sewer systems or electricity.
- The quality of building a house is considered as unprotected from cold or from other assault and completely against the required health conditions.
- Construction Forms, vary according to materials available in squatter settlements, some squatters houses formed of a simple building for low-income dwellers as shown in Figure (1)

Figure (1) Houses of Reeds huts forms built by squatters. (" (Mayada A.B Thesis (2008)

B. legal characteristics:

1) One of the basic characteristics of these settlements is the legal possession; these various settlements lack the most important feature of property which is being built on a building or a land that have been taken illegally (" (Mayada A.B Thesis (2008)

2) Al-Shareef, 2004, explained that the Islamic legislation banned encroachment, and

The appearance of abuses law is due to fallow land Islamic law, which means the ruined and disintegrating land that is neither possessed by anyone, a pasture, a wooding nor a park. It is the land that was not outlive, forbidden for outlive (road, construction, district ...etc.), or landfill.

THE THIRD PIVOT: A LOCAL EXAMPLE OF RESIDENTIAL SPRAWL AGAINST AGRICULTURAL LANDS

Locally, the study of (Mayada A.B Thesis (2008) is considered one of the comprehensive academic studies of squatter settlements in Iraq, especially of studying the morphological change of construction in Iraq resulted by existence of many squatter settlements in some districts in Baghdad. This study focused on the squatter settlements in the sever poverty areas whose high residential density in Russafah. As shown in figure (2).

Figure (2): Squatter Districts in Baghdad, 2008. (" (Mayada A.B Thesis (2008)

While, nowadays (within 7 years), a construction change has been taken place in other districts, and they were qualitatively expanded as well. The difference is distinguished with good multi-stories construction buildings. In addition, they were spread in high-class districts, which are not one of the poverty-class districts, as shown in figure (4).

Figure (3): Squatter Districts in Baghdad, 2013. Prepared by researchers according to municipality maps (Al-Mansoor, Al-A'damiyah, and Al-Kadhumiyah), and statistics (Baghdad municipality and Ministry of Planning).

The researchers selected palm orchard within Al-Karkh, Baghdad, especially Al-Shalichiyah, which is next to Al-Tobchy, Al-Eskan, as an example of residential sprawl of this type. There are many reasons to select this one:

1. This site witnessed fast residential sprawl within short period.
2. The statistical data are easy to reach, to perform the spatial analysis. In addition this district is located among high population district such as Al-Otaaifiyah, Al-Kadhumiyah, Al-Huria, and Al-Eskan.
3. The price of the land is close to the formal price, in spite of the fact that they are squatter land.
4. The statistical data necessary for the study topic are available, which would facilitate the work.

Figure (4): Squatter Districts within Al-Mansoor Municipality, Baghdad, 2013.

FIELD STUDY:

The researchers selected the case study of palm orchards and farms in Baghdad – Karkh specifically the area called Shalichiyah district. The main reasons for this selection are:

- 1- The location is close to Baghdad's city center in sectors (401,404,619) Karkh.
- 2- The area is surrounded by high-income and mid-income housing with relatively large build areas.
- 3- Surrounding districts have good infrastructure and social services.
- 4- The area is located on the administrative borders of Mansoor municipality and Kadhumiyah municipality.
- 5- The area is classified/registered as agricultural land.
- 6- Building type is good building close to low-cost housing.

The area differs from other slums/squatter settlements in that the building/construction materials and methods is classified as good with different finishing materials which in turn classified as very good (expensive), see figure 6. The houses could not be considered as temporary housing, rather it is closer to be a permanent building as it has long potential life span.

There were some important information acquired from the interviews with a number of households in the area. Almost all of the households/families interviewed living in the area come from large/extended families living in neighboring districts or were living there before relocating, also most of the new constructed houses in the slum area are better than the original housing units these families were living in before relocating in the slum area in terms of building materials and technique. 32% of interviewed households indicated that the main reason for purchasing the land and constructing the house in slum area is merely for investment purposes as the price of the housing unit doubles six times as soon as infrastructure services are formally connected to the new housing units especially with increasing demand on new housing units in Baghdad.

Figure 6: Pictures of housing units built in the slum area – (Eskan district) during the field trip

It is safe to say that building in slum area started to be acceptable by the community as there is no other solution to the housing crisis in Baghdad. Building housing units in city's outskirts is

not recommended as there is a lack of public services, infrastructure and long commute time to city center where are job opportunities are available.

Figure 7: More pictures of the housing units in the area under study.

URBAN SPRAWL SIZE ANALYSIS OF THE CASE STUDY:

With the development of statistical and geographic technology, it is possible to analyze the size and speed of urban sprawl in the area under study.

The researchers, drew a GIS map of the area through ArcGIS – ArcMap using the statistics and maps acquired from governmental organizations in Karkh including the municipalities of both Mansoor area and Khadhimia area as well as the Ministry of Planning. The map was then verified against satellite photos of the area and the field trip to the area.

The statistical data was then narrowed to only include data associated with the urban sprawl in the area from the survey made by the governmental organization mentioned earlier in 2002, 2010 and 2015. The data included number of building in the area (building density), Land use as registered by the government, estimated population. The data was check for errors then linked to the GIS shape file in order to produce two maps; the first illustrates the current land use as registered by the municipality and the ministry of planning (see figure 8). The second map shows land coverage (building density) from the year 2002 to the year 2015 (see figure 9).

Land use according to Karkh Municipalities

Figure 8: Land use according to Karkh Municipalities

Figure 9: Urban Sprawl/Housing on agricultural lands 2002-2015

PART 4: DISCUSSION

From the GIS maps shown above it is possible to observe the following:

- Most of the new housing units were built on agricultural land.
- The urban sprawl happened in an accelerated speed in the area; less than 25% of the agricultural land were built into new housing units between 2002-2010 (eight years), while more than 50% of the original agricultural land were built between 2010-2015 (five years).
- The urban sprawl started as a number scattered housing units on the borders of the agricultural land near the formal housing, the urban sprawl then developed into a more organized clusters of housing units along the unpaved roads (dirt roads) originally used for farming purposes.

Based on the general factors of urban sprawl discussed earlier in the research, the field study outcomes and GIS maps analysis, it is possible to summarize the main factors of urban sprawl in the area of Iskan-Shalchia into the following:

- Economic factors: most households have good financial income and reserves for building housing units that fulfill their needs despite the high building cost in Baghdad-Iraq compared with neighboring countries (Kahachi, 2012). In addition, building housing units on agricultural land is an investment with very good profits and low risk for others especially with rising demand on new housing projects close to the city center and the low fine rates by the authority which is about 1-22 USD only (act 154 in 2001), on the other hand there is a very low profit from farming in Iraq which further enhanced this kind of investments.
- Organizational factors: scarcity of housing lots/units provided by the government which generally do not meet Iraqi families needs for a number of reasons such as being far from city center, in areas with security problems, in areas where job opportunities are scarce or it does not meet the social requirements (Kahachi, 2012).
- Political factors: the lack of housing units and the resulting increase of housing demand was used by some politicians to achieve political interests. Some of the households reported that their housing lot was given for them in return of voting for specific political party in the election.
- Legal factors: there are few acts in the Iraqi laws which were put for humanitarian reasons especially for those in need of housing units, nevertheless, it was used by some people to legally buy and build on agricultural land. When analyzing the suggested "law of land ownership to those in need" it is possible to observe the following:

- a. Mentioning a very close date for giving land ownership to those in need who are living on governmental property. Although agricultural land was not included in the suggested law – Act 2 – 3, the law was received by those living in slums as a sign for giving them ownership of the land they are built on "*For those who built housing units informally before / / 2011 on land owned to the government or any municipalities within Iraqi cities masterplans the right to own the land after paying lots price as estimated by the government*" (Maher, 2015).
- b. Act 9 from the suggested law classifies the slum areas as reality for humanitarian purposes "*The municipality is committed to give building permission after giving the squatter household ownership according to laws, if the building quality of the house does not comply with the minimum requirements of building, the municipality should consider it as reality*" (Maher, 2015).
- c. Act 14 in the law gives authority for dealing with slums to administrative governmental organizations without including the real stakeholders and governmental/non-governmental organization responsible in the decision "*Municipalities' minster should put any necessary instructions to facilitate the implementation of the law and its acts*" (Maher, 2015).

The suggested law in general is publicly received by slum dwellers as an approval for their informal use of agricultural land for housing. It also promote investments in these areas.

On the other hand, when analyzing the Council of Ministers Resolution in 1st of October 2013, it is possible to observe the following:

- 1- Paragraph 1 from part 1; includes a clearly indicate that all agricultural land owned by the Ministry of Agriculture are affected by the resolution "*Squatter and slum settlers are given housing lots of 150 square meter in a good location as determined by the municipality of the city or the ministry of finance according to the specified conditions*" (IMN, 2015).
- 2- Paragraph 2 from part 1 could be easily circumvented by putting the land under the ownership of another person then reselling it "*a-Those who are covered with this law should first submit an application to the municipality which are responsible for the district where their squatter/slum house is built within 90 days of publishing this law. b- The person who submit the application should prove that neither him/her norany of his/herfamily members own any property*" (IMN, 2015).
- 3- Part 6 did not include any instructions about private agricultural land "*Removal of squatter/slum houses built on any lands that are dedicated for investment and regeneration projects as well as lands of archaeological, tourism and distinctive characteristics including the land numbered (535/ Atefia)*" (IMN, 2015).
- 4- Part 8 emphasize on building public awareness, however, the government do not hold legal accountability against public media due to misunderstanding of freedom of expression "*The people and general relations affairs department in the general secretariat of the council of ministers is responsible for raising public awareness campaign through media about the negative impacts of informal building and squatter/slum settlements on public land and properties and the legal consequences derived from.*" (IMN, 2015).

The resolution deals with slum dwellers as owners of the land basing that on humanitarian purposes without including any technical and engineering standards. In addition, there is administrative instructions to change the land use of any agricultural land with more than 50% housing to housing use (a formal copy of these instructions was shown to the researcher during the interview with one of the engineers in one of Baghdad's municipalities, however the

researcher could not get a copy of it. . Furthermore, according to the laws, these areas should be provided with the main infrastructure and services by the government.

CONCLUSIONS:

To summarize, the urban sprawl in the city of Baghdad and the increase in its speed is associated with a number of factors; social for safety and coherence of the family, political for achieving political interests, organizational for the lack of housing units/lots provided by the government and their mismatch between provided housing units/lots and family needs, and economic for achieving profit. In contrast with other slum dwellers, the study indicated that almost all households have very good economic support with sufficient income and reserves. The other type of factors is legal such as the lack of planning and imposing the laws without allowing frauds while dramatically increasing the rate of urban sprawl with unstudied/unplanned laws.

Although this phenomenon is helping to overcome the housing crisis in Baghdad, it has many potential disadvantages on living quality in the area and the city in general. Such disadvantages are:

- Health and services problems due to the unavailability or lack of infrastructure services in such areas and surrounding areas.
- Loss of large areas of agricultural land and green areas in the city which have many environmental impacts such as contributing to the desertification of the area.
- Cultural and social services problems due to the unavailability or lack of such services in these areas. This problem affects slum areas as well as the surrounding districts.
- High demand for job opportunities in the area as well increasing traffic jam in surrounding streets.

In addition to many other problems and issues such as legal problems, administrative issues which could be further researched in the future.

APPENDIX 1: QUESTIONNAIRE FOR INTERVIEW WITH SLUM SETTERS

Q1	Are you married? Do you have children?	
answer		
Q2	Do you own this house? Do you or your family own any other property?	
answer		
Q3	If you own this house then do you have any papers to prove your ownership?	
answer		
Q4	Were you living with an extended family?	
answer		
Q5	Did you build this housing unit? Did you build it?	
answer		
Q6	Was there any surveyors during the planning of the area or the streets?	
answer		
Q7	Where you living in the nearby area/districts?	
answer		
Q8	Are you satisfied with the building quality of the current housing unit?	
answer		
Q9	Were you aware of any help from the government for providing housing units/lots for you and your family?	
answer		
Q10	If you were offered a better housing unit, are you willing to leave this house?	
answer		
Q11	Do you expect the government to remove you from the area?	
answer		
Q12	Did any of your relatives live in slum areas on agricultural land before you?	
answer		
Q13	Did any governmental organizations or municipalities try to enforce anything on you or fine you due to living in informal housing?	
answer		
Q14	Did you buy/build this housing to live in or as a long-term investment?	
answer		
Q15	Do you expect any governmental organization to fine you in the future?	
answer		
Q16	Do you expect the housing unit to increase in price or not?	
answer		
Q17	Is your current housing unit better than your previous housing unit in terms of construction, area and location?	
answer		
Q18	Is your current housing unit better than your previous housing unit in terms of provided services and infrastructure?	
answer		

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ملخص البحث

هذا البحث هو دراسة علمية معمقة في تأثيرات الزحف العمراني على المناطق الزراعية في العراق إضافة الى كونها دراسة عملية في أسباب ذلك الزحف في خضم التغيرات السياسية و الاقتصادية التي يمر بها العراق ما بين سنة 2003 و 2015 مع الاخذ بنظر الاعتبار خصوصية الوضع الاجتماعي لسكان المنطقة. يكتسب هذا الموضوع أهميته من أهمية فهم التطورات المستقبلية للمدن و الريف. كما و يمكن الاستفادة من هذه الدراسة في وضع اليات لمعالجة الأسباب و الثغرات القانونية المؤدية لهذه الظاهرة بالإضافة الى وضع الاليات لحل المشاكل الناجمة عن الزحف العمراني كونها توفر فهما اوليا لمدى التأثيرات و علاقتها بالبيئة المحيطة على المدين القصير و البعيد وبالتالي تمكين معالجة هذه المشاكل و التقليل من التأثيرات عن طريق القوانين و الأنظمة و السياسات المتبعة من قبل الدولة.

ينتهج البحث منهج التحليل الجغرافي الاحصائي و الميداني حيث يعتمد المعلومات الإحصائية الجغرافية و الدراسة الميدانية كمصدر للبيانات و التي يتم تحليلها لاحقا باستخدام نظام المعلومات الجغرافية من اجل تحقيق دراسة معمقة حول المشكلة البحثية مرورا بمجموعة من الأهداف هي:

1. تعريف مقتضب حول الزحف العمراني، تأريخه، و اثاره المحتملة عموما و تأثير تغيير النظام السياسي و الاقتصادي و الاجتماعي على الزحف العمراني في العراق خصوصا.
 2. استعراض البحوث الاكاديمية حول الزحف العمراني على مستوى العالم و العراق على الخصوص و اهم الأسباب المؤدية الى تفحل هذه الظاهرة.
 3. استعراض الثغرات القانونية التي تم تمرير التجاوز على الأراضي الزراعية من خلالها مع استعراض القوانين المتغاض عن تنفيذها لأسباب إنسانية.
 4. اختيار موقع الدراسة (بساتين النخيل في جانب الكرخ من بغداد) / المجاورة لمناطق "الطوبجي، الإسكان، مدخل الكاظمية" كمثال على الزحف العمراني منذ سنة 2003 و الى سنة 2015 و تحليل التحولات التي طرأت على المنطقة من خلال نظام الـ GIS. و من ثم دراسة هذه التحولات و فهم اثارها على الريف و على المدينة.
- ينتهي البحث بمجموعة من الاستنتاجات و التوصيات النهائية و مقترحات لبحوث مستقبلية حول موضوع الدراسة.